

**THE PROSPECTS FOR A BALANCED RESOURCE COLLECTION OVER THE WAYS OF
COMBINED VILIGOVATION OF METALS FROM SUB-CONDITIONAL ORES****Lyashenko V.,***candidate technical Sciences, State enterprise "Ukrainian Research and Design and Intelligence Institute of Industrial Technology",**Zhovti Vody, Dnipropetrovsk region,**ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-8361-4179>***Dudar T.,***Sciences, prof. Head of the Environmental Sciences Department, National Aviation University, Kyiv**ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-3114-9732>.***Stus V.,***doctor of medical sciences, professor, Professor of the Department of Surgery No. 1 and Urology of the Dnipro State Medical University, Dnipro,**ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-4539-8126>***Shapovalov V.,***candidate technical Sciences, Associate Professor, Associate Professor of the Department of Occupational Safety and Civil Safety Kryvyi Rih National University,**Kryvyi Rih, Dnipropetrovsk region**ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-5965-2869>***Olynyk T.***Senior Professor, Head of the Department of Mineral Processing, Kryvyi Rih National University, Kryvyi Rih, Dnipropetrovsk region**ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-0315-7308>**h-index 5 Scopus Author ID: 36173274800, h-index 7 Google Scholar <http://surl.li/snyll>***ABSTRACT**

The main scientific and practical results of research and implementation of technologies of underground block leaching of metals from rock ores in underground mine installations are given. Technological schemes of mining technology and PBV are described. An assessment of the obtained research results is given, their positive and negative indicators that determine the efficiency and environmental safety of the PBV process are substantiated, as well as the dependences of the explosion parameters on the average linear size of a piece of the detonated ore mass are established. It is justified that the use of mining and chemical technology should be considered a promising direction for the development of deposits of poor rock ores. The development of experimental unit 5–86 at the Ingulska mine of SE «Eastern GZK», Ukraine, in which 8,248 tons of rock ore were struck, confirmed the possibility of PBV and the validity of the preparation scheme (the maximum deviation of the actually measured class $-25+0$ mm is 7.2%). It was established that the most intense infiltration leaching occurs in the size class of ore pieces $-100 + 0$ mm. For the conditions of the Michurinsky deposit, the recommended yield of this fraction in the reflected ore is about 90%. Metals from fractions $-200 + 100$ mm are extracted less intensively and longer. The recommended ore yield of this class is 10%. It is proved that the main place in the technology of PBV should be occupied by explosive ore preparation operations, which ensure effective extraction of metal from stored ores in the chamber. Technological operations for the formation of cutting gaps and compensation spaces, as well as ensuring optimal loosening of stored ore under leaching conditions are regulated by the volume of ore released from the block (up to 30%). To neutralize and wash the spent ore mass, it is recommended to treat it with lime solution and mine water through wells for supplying leaching solutions (irrigation system). Protection of the hydrogeological environment should be carried out by silting the bottom of the chamber for collecting productive solutions with a clay solution and constant monitoring of mine water pollution in the area of impact of PBV. On the basis of the received positive results of the research and implementation of technologies of PBV of metals from hard ores during the development of block 5–86, in accordance with the issued recommendations, the same approach was used for blocks 5–84–86 and 5–88–90, as well as industrial and experimental block 1-75-79 (SE «Eastern GZK», Ukraine). Due to the involvement in the production of substandard ores, the raw material base of metal extraction at the operating mines can be increased by 1.4–1.6 times. Research results can be used during the underground development of ore deposits of out-of-balance and out-of-condition ores of complex structure.

It is noted that the combined technologies include the organization of two specialized underground sites (the first - for ore enrichment; the second - PBV blocks for leaching metals) and two above ground (the first - for separation and processing of off-balance ore dumps in surface warehouses of mines on modular installations; commercial leaching; on the earth's surface) can be used during the underground development of ore deposits of out-of-balance and out-of-condition ores of complex structure.

Prospects for research. To continue the scientific and design-technological support for the development of grain production to process substandard and out-of-balance, instead of bark components, stocks of genus for their industrial production with the stagnation of combined technologies. Such technologies are effective if 40% of the

rich ore is exposed to the earth's surface, and 60% of the poor, substandard and unbalanced ore is deposited underground.

Keywords: combined technologies, ore crushing, metal precipitating, efficiency, environmental management.

INTRODUCTION

One of the problems of the mining industry is the high cost of ore mining and processing. On the other hand, the ores that are mined belong to the class of poor and poor in the content of useful components. The efficiency of metal extraction can be increased by introducing an integrated technology, including a traditional chamber mining system with a hardening backfill and in-situ block leaching (IBL) from rock ores [1, 2]. Therefore, improving technology and justifying the parameters of underground mining, ensuring increased economic efficiency and environmental safety, is an urgent scientific, practical and social task [3, 4]. The main scientific and practical results have been extracted under the hour of scientific and research work on the topics (scientific ceramics – V.I. Lyashenko): (Advanced and development of technology for the development of gironic mass, which will ensure the tasks of the granulometric warehouse for underground block formation of uranium ores" ("Geotechnology ") – state registration number No. 0105U001957; "Advanced development of seismic-safe technology for the preparation of ore mass before underground block laying of deposits 1, 4, 5,10 in the 280–210 m Michurinskoye version of the Indian family" – state registration number No. 0108U008931) and others. This work is a continuation of research with the participation of the authors, the main scientific and practical results of which are most fully presented in works [5, 6].

The purpose of the work is to study and implement combined technologies for underground block leaching of metals from broken strong ores in underground mine installations, ensuring rational use and protection of subsoil, increasing efficiency and environmental safety as a result of the use of a traditional chamber system with a hardening filling mixture of various compositions and strengths in combination with PBB.

To achieve this goal, it is necessary to solve the following tasks:

- establish the intensity of infiltration leaching of metal from ores depending on the size class of ore pieces;

- prove the effectiveness of metal extraction by leaching it from stored ores in a chamber using drilling and blasting ore preparation;

- propose combined technologies for leaching metals from broken substandard ores in mining installations;

- provide scientific support for the preparation and testing of PBB pilot and industrial experimental blocks.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

In the research process, a complex method was used, including an analytical approach using the fundamentals of system analysis and mathematical statistics, performing technological experiments using economic and mathematical modeling, technical and economic calculations and pilot industrial implementation. The

method of complex generalization, assessment of practical experience and scientific achievements in the field of geotechnology, theory and practice of explosive destruction of solid media was also used. Methods of continuum mechanics and research techniques for assessing wave processes have been implemented using standard methods developed by leading specialists from developed mining countries with the participation of the authors [7, 8].

Object of study and its technological audit.

Mining technology. Near-surface reserves of the Michurinskoye deposit of the State Enterprise "Vostochny GOK" (Ukraine), a significant part of which lies under the river. Ingul, industrial and civil buildings and structures, are represented by steeply dipping ore bodies of varying thickness. The length of the ore bodies is from 600 to 700 m along the strike (mostly 100–250 m), along the dip from 150 to 400 m. The ores and their host rocks are strong, massive, and have a non-layered structure. Strength coefficient f on the prof. scale. M. M. Protodyakonova from 14 to 18. In the direction towards the surface there is a significant deterioration in the quantitative and qualitative characteristics of fracturing both in individual deposits and in the field as a whole. On the upper horizons the rocks are weathered, the f factor decreases to 6. The deposit is developed using a chamber system with filling of the mined-out space with a hardening mixture.

Mining operations are carried out at a depth of 40–50 to 350 m. The chambers are mined in sublevels 10–15 m high. Ore is broken with borehole charges with diameters of 57 and 65 mm. Wells are drilled using NT–2 and PK–75 rigs. Parallel downward wells with a diameter of 85 and 105 mm for the formation of cutting slots are drilled using NKR–100 M machines (Ukraine). Self-propelled drilling, loading and hauling and auxiliary equipment from Atlas Copco, Tamrock and others are also used [9, 10].

Geochemical technologies. When implementing mining technologies in combination with PBB, leaching schemes from permeable ores in natural occurrence through wells drilled from the surface are widely used. It is also possible to use schemes with preliminary crushing of rock ores by blasting explosives. The authors propose the introduction of a new, cheaper technology for the extraction and processing of low-grade and out-of-balance ores in terms of the content of the useful component, consisting of a traditional chamber system with a hardening filling mixture of various compositions and strengths, as well as PBB. Geochemical technologies for metal leaching provide for the supply of a leaching solution (in this case, these are low-concentration solutions of sulfuric acid to the ore-containing material, as well as the preparation of a receiving horizon in the form of a bottom, silted with a clay solution at an angle of up to 5–6° to the horizontal. The time for metal leaching is from 6 to 8 months After this, the productive solution is collected in containers and sent

for subsequent processing to a hydrometallurgical plant (HMZ), and the leached material is left in waste chambers as a backfill mixture with a strength of up to 1 MPa and washed with water through the existing irrigation system to reduce release into the geological environment. harmful substances [11, 12].

The effectiveness of the application of this technology is achieved with the following basic mining-geological and mining-technical characteristics of ore deposits: stable and moderately stable steeply dipping ore bodies located in rocky acid-water-resistant host rocks; according to the quality (content of useful component) of ore - balance, poor and off-balance; fracture zones in the near-block space are poorly developed, the carbonate content is no more than 2–4%; ore deposits have significant off-balance halos in the absence of clay inclusions. The most common technological operations

for PMB of metal from ores are given in Table. 1 [13, 14].

Ore body 2 is divided into production blocks, and mining and cutting operations are carried out. Create a cutting slot and a flat bottom of the chamber. Drilling is carried out in parallel fans of holes with a diameter of 50–85 mm from sublevel workings 9. Partial (up to 30%) gravity release of stored ore 8 is carried out to the haulage horizon through ore outlet workings located in the lower part of the production block, and then transported by loading and delivery machines. After breaking ore 8, an irrigation system is installed in the upper part of chamber 1, consisting of a set of pipes 11 and nozzles for supplying leaching solutions, and in the lower part, workings 7 (sumps) are equipped for collecting productive solutions [15, 16].

Table 1.

Technological operations of underground block leaching of metal from ores

Mining enterprise (deposit, mine)	Beginning of development of PBB technology	Technological operations			
		Ore preparation Without destroying the ore massif	Supply of leaching solutions	Issuance of productive solutions	Transportation of resin to GMZ
Lermontov Mining and Chemical Mining Administration (Bykogorskoe)	1963 g.	Ore chipping by blasting	From a sorption column placed on the day surface	Into a sorption column placed on the day surface	In tanks
PJSC PIMCU (Strel'tsovskoe ore field)	1983 g.	Ore chipping by blasting	Same	Same	Same
JSC "TsGKHK" (Zvezdnoye, Vostok, Semizbay)	1968 g.	The same	– " –	– " –	– " –
SE "VostokGOK" (Michurinskoye, Ingul'skaya mine)	1999 g.	– " –	From a sorption column placed in the mine workings of the irrigation horizon	From the collection sump to the sorption column located in the mine workings of the irrigation horizon	In trolleys to the earth's surface and then in tanks at the GMZ

The supply of leaching solutions to the chamber is carried out until its standard concentration is reached in the productive solution (up to approximately 4 months). Collection of productive solutions and their delivery for hydrometallurgical processing is carried out upon reaching the standard concentration of metal in the productive solution.

The hardware diagram for the industrial development of PBB technology contains: a railway tank; pumps F430 PP – 50/38; X 80–50–250 E; PR63; AX 125–100–400E and X50–32–125; container for low-grade acid; drainage device; tanker and resin container; submersible pump F–706 PP–185; sumps for productive leaching solutions and their neutralization; hydraulic lift; containers with a volume of 0.4 and 0.8 m³;

sorption column type SNK; pipeline; ejector; free capacity; containers for acidification and neutralization; manual hoist with a lifting capacity of up to 1 ton.

DISCUSSION AND RESULTS

The set of technological equipment for water treatment at the Ingul'skaya mine of the State Enterprise "VostokGOK" contains: sorption columns of the SNK type; pump tanks 0.4 m³ with pump AX; several containers with ion-exchange resin and diluted sulfuric acid (developed by the research and production complex "Automation and Mechanization", manufactured jointly with the mechanical repair plant of the State Enterprise "VostokGOK", Ukraine). The proposed technology for the development of low-permeability rock massifs of the PBB is carried out as follows (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Technological diagram of metal leaching from rock ores in installations located in mine workings: 1 – camera; 2 – ore body; 3, 4 – horizontal and vertical workings; 5 – insulating material; 6 – insulating jumper; 7 – capacity; 8 – stored ore; 9 – production; 10 – insulating jumper; 11 – pipeline; 12 – devices for sorption processing of productive solutions; 13 – container for preparing the leaching solution; 14 – niches; 15 – pumps; 16 – pipe; 17 – metal desorption apparatus

After completion of the leaching process of stored ores in the chamber, process water is supplied to the leached material from wells to supply leaching solutions (irrigation system). The leached material is left in the chambers as a filling mixture. Its uniaxial compressive strength reaches 1 MPa. To increase its strength, it is coated with a hardening solution. The protection of the hydrogeological environment is carried out by organizing constant monitoring of groundwater pollution through observation wells drilled at the bottom of the production block and to contacts with the ore body, as well as to zones of fracturing and hydrogeological rupture of rocks within the influence of the PBB [17, 18].

Unlike known technologies and technical means for leaching metals from rock ores, leaching and productive solutions are pumped from the underlying to the overlying horizon without releasing them onto the earth's surface. The products are delivered to the earth's surface in trolleys in the form of resin for further processing at the GMZ. Essentially, the mine is equipped with an underground section for leaching metals from rock ores in PMB blocks and installations located in underground workings. The authors indicate that this method can significantly reduce the operations used in the traditional mining system (except for such as the creation of compensation space, release and delivery of up to 30% of stored ore from the PBB chamber, etc.).

Experimental testing of block 5–86 PBB. The complex of works for its preparation included the following operations: driving of threaded and drilling workings; drilling of the wells; penetration of cut-off risers; formation of cutting slots and compensation space; breaking of ores with borehole charges and their subsequent storage. The block had the following parameters: height 20 m; width 16 m; length 24 m. When preparing for the PMB, the authors recommended the possibility of maximizing the use of previously completed mine workings. To the mountains –210 m there is a sorption column with a container for receiving sorbent, a main pipeline with a sprinkler system for supplying leaching solutions to the stored ore into the PBB chamber (Figure 2). [19, 20].

To the mountains –255 m pumping stations with sumps for neutralization solutions, preparation, additional acidification and capture of productive solutions are equipped. From the mountains –280 m wells were drilled to monitor changes in the hydrogeological environment and conduct appropriate monitoring. In this mode, working solutions from the irrigation horizon (210 m horizon) are supplied to the surface of the ore stored in a block through a system of perforated polyethylene pipes with a diameter of 16 mm.

Figure 2. Technological scheme for preparing the block before installation:
 1–sorption column; 2– capacity for receiving sorbent; 3 – main pipeline; 4 – grinding drill bits;
 5–camera PBB; 6–pumping station; 7, 8, 9 – sumps for extraction, apparently, neutralization, preparation and
 acidification and catching of productive waste; 10 – catching horizon; 11–Sverdlovins for monitoring the
 contamination of groundwater; 12–contour of ore body; 13 – leveling horizon

The pipes were inserted into 48 wells drilled from the mountains. 210 m down into the block chamber. The total length of these wells is 309.2 m, the network of irrigation points is 2×2 m. Irrigation is carried out periodically for 30 minutes with pauses of 2–3 hours. During pauses, favorable conditions are created for aeration of the ore material and the development of oxidative processes that facilitate the transition of metal from sparingly soluble tetravalent form into a readily soluble hexavalent form. The irrigation density during the experiment varied from 9 to 16 l/(m²·h), which provided an infiltration irrigation regime.

Geochemical technology at the PMB pilot site includes the following operations: irrigation and acidification of broken ore with sulfuric acid solutions; sorption of metal from productive solutions onto resin (regenerated anion exchanger of the AMP brand); intensification of leaching processes by shaking explosions; pumping through the main mine drainage of excess solutions after sorption to the mine water treatment plant (WTP); neutralization and washing of the spent ore mass with lime solution and mine water. The leaching process is ensured by technological equipment, including: surface unit; technical complex for receiving and dispensing acid and resin; underground node; technological complex of leaching and sorption. Sulfuric acid from a railway tank used as a supply tank is periodically pumped through an intermediate tank and a drain device into a transport trolley – a tank. A tank car with acid is lowered down the shaft to the mountain. 210 m. Acid is dosed in accordance with the technological regulations at the horizon. 240 m in the sump of productive solutions – for preparing the leaching solution [21, 22].

The circulating leaching solution is pumped from the mountains. 240 m into the block irrigation system. Irrigation is carried out through wells drilled in the ceiling of the block chamber. The solution seeps through the entire mass of crushed ore and drains along the drift ditch into the sump of productive solutions. After the

productive solutions are saturated with leached metal, the solutions are pumped into a column for sorption, where the metal settles in the resin. A control catch of resin “slip” is carried out on the screen and, in the form of a filtrate, it is fed into the mother liquor for additional strengthening with acid, from where it is pumped back into the irrigation system and then into the block chamber. Occasionally, when there is an excess of productive solutions in the sump due to water inflow, part of the solutions (in a volume of up to 10 m³) after sorption is neutralized with lime in the neutralization sump and then pumped into the general drainage ditch of the drift. From it, the solution is supplied for dilution to the settling tank of the main drainage basin of the mine with further pumping to the water treatment plant.

Periodically, the saturated resin from the sorption column is unloaded into a special tank car and raised to the surface, where, using “transport” water from the pump, it is sent by gravity to a tank truck with a volume of 6.4 m³ and transported for regeneration to the hydrometallurgical plant. The regenerated resin is loaded into the trolley from the tank truck by gravity – using recycled water, which drains from the trolley or tank truck through a cartridge filter during loading. At the haulage horizon, the resin is fed from a tank car into the sorption column by airlift. After completion of leaching, washing and neutralization of the block, insulating and ventilation bridges are constructed in all adjacent workings at horizons 280, 240 and 210 m to prevent the emanation of radon and other harmful substances. Research has established that after leaching there was a change in the granulometric composition of the ores. The leached ore, after being delivered from the block to wagons and transported to the surface, was carefully classified on a screen through changing sieves at the ore processing plant (OPF), collected and weighed by fraction. The granulometric characteristics of the leached ore differ both from the parameters specified by calculation and from the values obtained after breaking in the block (Table 2).

Table 2.

Metal content and recovery by size class in leached ore

Index	Size class, mm				
	-200+150	-150+100	-100+50	-50+25	-25+0
Class yield, %	8,8	17,0	27,0	35,3	11,9
Metal content, %	0,038	0,038	0,030	0,025	0,014
Metal recovery, %	26,3	26,3	33,3	40,0	71,4

When developing experimental block 5–86, experimental blocks 5–84–86 and 5–88–90, as well as industrial experimental block 1–75–79, in accordance with the recommendations issued, previously completed workings were used to the maximum. After restoration and repair work on previously excavated workings, special attention should be paid to the development of an irrigation horizon located in the area of intensive influence of spent blocks. The ore massif in the 197–210 m level is weakened by the threaded and clearing workings that existed before the preparation of the blocks for water treatment, as well as by the network of wells of the irrigation system being created. In

these workings, systematic monitoring was organized over their stability and the nature of the stress–strain state of the boundary massif (geomechanical monitoring). Based on the results of extensive research carried out on a complex of scientific and research work during the underground development of genera in energy-damaged massifs, the authors propose the rozrunkov formula for structuring the parameters of brown–vibuch robots and safety the main parameters of the chambers from the regulation of the effectiveness of PBB metals (Table 3).

Table 3.

Safe camera parameters for ore deposits

Parameter names	Calculation formulas
The line of least resistance, m	$W = K_{mp} \cdot \frac{90}{\sqrt{f}} \cdot \sqrt{\frac{e}{e_{3m} \cdot m}} \cdot d_{CKB}$
The coefficient of convergence of wells should be taken in the range of 1.5–2.5, taking into account the influence of mining technical and technological factors	$m = 3,0 - K \cdot \frac{h}{B} \cdot d_{CKB}$
The distance between the ends of the wells in the fan, m	$a = m \cdot W$
Recalculation of LNS, m	$w_n = \sqrt{\frac{a \cdot W}{m_n}}$
The length of the operational block l to achieve the specified quality of mining mass crushing, m	$l = 2(K+m) + \theta_1$
The width of the compensation space during the explosion in the clamp is determined by the width of the cut-off gap θ_0 and the length of the partial release section l_0 , limited by the expansion coefficient $1.15 > K < 1.2$, m	$\theta_1 = \theta_0 + 2l_0$
The effective height h of the stored mining mass in the PBV, taking into account the technological and hydrodynamic characteristics of leachable ores, m	$h = \frac{\theta \times t}{V \times \gamma}$
<p>Note: W – is the line of least resistance, m; K_{mp} – is a coefficient that takes into account the fissuring of the rock massif (varies from 0.95 to 1.1); f – is the strength coefficient of rocks according to the scale of Prof. M.M. Protodiakonova, unit.; e_{3m} – volume concentration of energy for the reference BP (accepted ammonite No. 6ZhV), kcal/cm³ ($e = A_{BB} \cdot \rho$); e – the same, for the applied BP, kcal/cm³ ($e = A_{BB} \cdot \rho$); d_{CKB} – diameter of wells, cm; m – coefficient of convergence of charges (varies from 1.0 to 1.3), units; A_{3T} i A_{BB} – complete ideal work of the explosion of the reference and applied BP, respectively, kcal/h; p – charge density (varies from 0.8 for BP type gramonite 79/21; granulite AS-4; AS-4B; AS-8; AS-8B to 1.6 – for rock ammonite No. 1, etc.), g /cm³; h – the maximum size of the floor for a specific block, m; B – block (camera) width, m; K – is a coefficient that depends on the h/B ratio and other mining technical factors: with $h/B = 1.05$, $K = 0.13$; when $h/B > 1.3$, $K = 0.10$; m_n – new convergence coefficient, unit; θ_1 – the size of the compensation space, m; θ – irrigation mode, m³/m²•time; t – time of intensive leaching, hours; V – reagent consumption per 1 ton of ore, m³; γ – density of leaching ores, t/m³. an hour.</p>	

Metal extraction ε significantly depends on the average linear size of a piece of blasted ore d_{av} and can be described with a high degree of confidence ($R^2 = 0.97$) by an expression of the form: $\varepsilon = 11,817d_{cp}^{-0,4501}$. A distinctive feature of determining the destruction parameters of rock ores with a given crushing quality for

leaching is finding the required explosion energy, taking into account the maximum energy intensity of rock crushing. The pattern described above is important when controlling subsequent parameters of the leaching process. One of the factors that makes it possible to reduce the average linear size of a piece and increase the

newly formed area of the destroyed rock mass is the preparation of the ore mass for leaching using the kinetic energy of flying pieces of rock, followed by breaking the ore in a clamp [23, 24]. An example of

calculating the parameters of drilling and blasting operations and borehole charges was carried out for horizons, workings, fans and production blocks 5–84–86 are given in Table. 4.

Table 4.

Calculation data for borehole explosive charges for the production unit

Number of fan, row of well	Number wells	Length wells, (L),m	The amount of under-charging, m	Chargeable length parts of wells (L ₃), m	Well charge mass, kg		Quantity electrodetonators, detonating cord, units	Number deceleration series, ms	Well diameter, mm
					granular	патрированное			
FIRST EXPLOSION									
Horizon 240 m. Ort drilling									
16	1	5,5	1,5	4	26	0,6			
	2	5,5	3	2,5	16	0,6			
	3	5,5	1,5	4	26	0,6			
	4	6,5	3	3,5	23	0,6			
	5	8	1,5	6,5	42	0,6			
	6	9,5	3	6,5	42	0,6			
	7	12	15	10,5	68	0,6			
	8	13	3	10	65	0,6			
	9	12,5	1,5	11	72	0,6			
	10	12	3	9	59	0,6			
	11	12	1,5	10,5	68	0,6			
	12	12	3	9	59	0,6			
	13	12	1,5	10,5	68	0,6			
	14	12,5	3	9,5	62	0,6			
	15	13	1,5	11,5	75	0,6			
	16	14	3	11	72	0,6			
	17	12	1,5	10,5	68	0,6			
	18	9,5	3	6,5	42	0,6			
	19	7,5	1,5	6	39	0,6			
	20	6,5	3	3,5	23	0,6			
	21	6	1,5	4,5	29	0,6			
	22	6	3	3	20	0,6			
Total		227,5	63	164,5	1064	13	44	2 (75)	85

During the experiment, about 54% of the metal reserves in the block were transferred into solution at an acid consumption of 36% of the design one. Thus, in modern economic conditions, the extraction and processing of ores using traditional technologies is inappropriate if the metal content in the mined ordinary ore is less than 0.070 c.u.e. The advantages of block leaching compared to traditional ore mining and processing technology are the absence of costs for individual operations, namely [25, 26]:

–during mining: secondary crushing and ore release; in-mine transportation of ore;

–delivery of ore to the surface; crushing and beneficiation of ore; backfilling of mined-out space; loading into railway cars and transportation to GMZ;

–during processing at GMZ: ore reloading; its grinding; leaching; sorption; resin regeneration; tailings storage.

To neutralize and wash the spent ore mass, it is recommended to treat it with a solution of lime and

mine water through wells for supplying leaching solutions (irrigation system). It is necessary to continue research based on data from hydrogeological monitoring of the environment in the zone of influence of the PBB (including groundwater pollution) through observation wells drilled at the bottom of the production block and to contacts with the ore body, as well as to zones of fracturing and hydrogeological rupture of rocks within the influence of the PBB [27, 28].

Thus, the introduction of PBB on an industrial scale will significantly improve the economic indicators of production activities, which would allow, through the modernization of fixed assets and technical reequipment of production, to involve in the development of reserves of poor, substandard and off-balance ores and extend the life of existing mines. Based on the positive results of the research and development of PBB technologies for metals from mineral ores during the development of block 5–86, a change of mind was made to promote combined underground and surface technologies the wholesale deposition of metals during

the preparation of low-grade ores, brought to the balance level for the traditional method (Figure 3).

Promising areas of research. To ensure the protection of the hydrogeological environment, it is necessary to silt the bottom of the chamber for collecting productive solutions with a clay solution, as well as construct semi-active water-permeable chemically active barriers (WCAB) and use biological technologies for

PWB. If necessary, it is possible to use an anti-filtration curtain, constructed, for example, using the “wall in the ground” technology [11]. This should ensure a reduction in the degree of metal contamination of ground and surface waters, soils and sediments, including the main Michurinsky fault (Kropyvnytskyi, Ukraine). Research should also be continued to develop technologies that would satisfy both economic and environmental requirements [29, 30].

Figure 3. Combined mining of ore deposits: 1, 2 – similar, rich and poor in place of the bark component of the ore; 3 – complex of bulk mining of poor and off-balance ores; 4, 5 – obviously, ore – control and enrichment station (RCS) and factory (ROF); 6 – mortgage complex; 7 – workshop for the preparation of wildflower products

CONCLUSION

1. It is substantiated that when mining low-grade rock ore deposits, the introduction of the proposed mining and chemical technology should be considered a promising direction. The experience of mining the pilot block 5–86 at the Ingulskaya mine of the State Enterprise “VostokGOK”, in which 8248 tons of rock ore was extracted, confirmed the possibility of implementing the PMB and the validity of the scheme for its preparation (the maximum deviation of the actually measured class $-25+0$ mm is 7.2%).

2. It has been established that the most intense infiltration leaching occurs when the size class of ore pieces is $-100 + 0$ mm. For the Michurinskoye deposit of the State Enterprise “VostokGOK” the recommended yield of this fraction in the crushed ore is about 90%. Metals are extracted less intensively and over a longer period of time from the $-200 +100$ mm fractions. The recommended yield of ore of this size class is 10%.

The main indicators of block leaching are given in Table. 5.

Table 5.

Main indicators of block leaching

Name of indicators	Meaning of indicators	Name of indicators
Volume of ore leached, thousand tons		8,248
Metal content, cu. e.		0.065
Acid consumption H ² SO ₄ , t		231.1
Specific acid consumption, kg/t		28.0
Acid consumption for acidification, t		27.8
Specific consumption of oxidizer, kg/t		3.3
Acidification time, days		40
Amount of solutions supplied for irrigation, m ³		66106
Irrigation density, l/(m ² ·h)		1,6
F:T ratio		8:1
Irrigation time, days		166
Duration of sorption, days		398
Volume of solutions for sorption, m ³		25756
Characteristics of productive solutions:		-
uranium concentration, average, mg/l		220
sulfuric acid content, average, g/l		13.5
pH value, average		3.2
Characteristics of irrigation solutions, g/l:		-
Fe ⁺³ /Fe ⁺² concentration		1.i/0.38
Mineralization (dry residue)		43.2
Volume of metal-saturated anion exchange resin, m ³		101.3
Average capacity of saturated sorbitol,		27.3
Residual capacity for sorbent metal after regeneration, kg/m ³		0.66
Duration of tailings washing in the block, days		65
Volume of wash water, m ³		5775
Specific water consumption for washing, m ³ /t		0.7

3. The proposed geochemical technology was applied by the State Enterprise "UkrNIPromtekhologii" with scientific support for the preparation and development of PBB of experimental blocks 5–86, 5–84–86 and 5–88–90, as well as the industrial experimental block 1–75–79 at Michurinsky deposit of the State Enterprise "VostokGOK".

4. The development of combined technologies includes the organization of two specialized underground mills (the first – for ore enrichment; the other – PBB units for bending metals) and two above-ground ones (the first – for separation and processing in off-balance sheet ores at the surface warehouses of mines in modular installations; formation of metals on the earth's surface).

5. *Prospects for research.* To continue the scientific and design-technological support for the development of grain production to process substandard and out-of-balance, instead of bark components, stocks of genus for their industrial production with the stagnation of combined technologies. Such technologies are effective if 40% of the rich ore is exposed to the earth's surface, and 60% of the poor, substandard and unbalanced ore is deposited underground.

The authors give a lot of credit for the fate of the following robots: Tarkhina Yu. M., Khudoshiniy N. O., Lyashenko L. A., Dudchenko A. Kh., Tkachenko A. A. (DP "UkrNDPRIPROMTECHNOLOGIES", Ukraine), Pukhalsky V. M., Kuchi P. M., Kopanev A. V., Senchuk V. V., Merkulov V. A. (DP "SkhidGZK"), as well

as valuable and constructively respected recommendations to the reviewers of the statistics.

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